

Hioz

Hioz LLC

651 N Broad St, Suite 205 #186

Middletown, Delaware 19709

hello@hioz.co

www.hioz.co/

Written by Joseph Hayes on February 20th, 2021.

What Social Network Usage Can Say About The Status Quo, A Hioz Publication

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1. ABSTRACT

Background

With social networks becoming more of an embodiment over our culture, our research endeavors to describe the systematic influence for the behavior on social networks with members of different social classes, and the psychological processes that justify those behaviors. We offer a framework in our research (N = 512) to elaborate our findings regarding the diverse usages that members of different social classes have with social networks, and we propose that their behavior on them involves the co-occurrence of two independent options—the perceived desire for creating and discovering new individuals and content, and the perceived desire for strengthening or maintaining existing relationships by staying up to date with them.

Methods

We gathered digital data through data exports and data downloads from each participant's account on each involved social network, and measured the number of contacts they've communicated with in the last 90 days, the geographic locations of those contacts (if public), and how frequently they've talked to those contacts in the last 90 days. Interview data was also gathered by exploring the views of study participants in relation to their digital data, its results & its conclusions.

Results

As a first test of our perspective on social network usage from users in different social classes, our research explored the behaviors of participants on social networks. In higher-class participants there was a far higher desire to create and discover, with more frequent exploration for content and new contacts, and with less frequent chats towards existing contacts - which were mostly longer distance and belonging to a loose circle. While in lower-class participants, there was a far higher desire to strengthen and maintain, with more time dedicated to communicating with existing friends in their local community or viewing their posts to stay up to date with them, and with less frequent chats towards new individuals. These differences captured the goals and behaviors associated with participants that were striving for usages on social networks that were most applicable to their needs based upon their social class contexts.

Conclusion

These findings suggest that while higher-class individuals focus their efforts on using social networks to discover new content and individuals, lower-class individuals focus their efforts to maintain and strengthen their existing circles and connections - and to stay up to date with their life events via posts. In discussions, higher-class participants perceived their choices made on social networks as being made from their desires for entertainment, meeting new people, and learning new things. Lower-class participants, however, perceived their choices made on social networks as being made from necessity for a robust set of contacts based on their life circumstances.

2. BACKGROUND

Social networks are quickly becoming the 'gold standard' for communication mediums in our contemporary world, with just over 50% of the world's population having at least one social network account [1], and with the average social network user holding more than 8 social network accounts [2]. Needless to say, the social network landscape has seen rapid development in new products - and a rapid adoption of their existing products over the years. As an example, just the Facebook-owned products Messenger and WhatsApp contributed to more than 60 billion messages sent every day in 2016 [3] with only exponential growth since. The world has gotten more connected as a direct result of social networks, and they are here to stay because of it.

But during the development and adoption of social networks, its impact within several sociological processes was overlooked by its creators, including its role within the sociological framework that powers connectivity itself in most contemporary societies; social class.

Social class is a cornerstone element for much of society's functions within our contemporary world, and has been an area of study for several decades as a result. From the works of Aha! Process Inc. [4], Ruby Payne [5], and several other academics, we have been better able to understand the causes, impacts, and tendencies of varying social classes and their members. And with these understandings, we've been able to offer more coherent approaches to tackle systemic social class discrepancies (like poverty) in recent years; such as comprehensive welfare programs, standardized education,

lower-class community projects, and self-improvement plans for members of lower-class communities.

There is established precedent in measuring the growth of human and social capital within communities & individuals, and for assessing the improvements made over time to them as a result of an implementation of progressive solutions to their class-based conflicts. For instance, in a study [6] conducted by Dr. Ruby Payne, by following the concepts and tools from *Getting Ahead in a Just-Gettin'-By World* by Phil DeVol and *Framework* by Ruby Payne, the YWCA of Saint Joseph County, IN had seen phenomenal results on adults in their community from the program. In a span of 6 months from participants; income saw a 84% increase, education saw a 69% increase, employment saw a 63% increase, and support systems saw an 84% increase.

There have also been internet-based studies on how different social classes utilize their time online [7], with these studies showing a higher focus from lower-class individuals to use their time online for entertainment - mostly video games, and with a higher focus from higher-class individuals to use their time online for information and news. And despite social networks playing a major role online, no research has yet been conducted regarding how different social classes interact with social networks in certain quantitative measures. To be clear, the justification for this research isn't unfounded, since several social networks have turned their cheek to the varying levels of usages and effects that their services have across social classes, and its severity. From consequences as inadvertent as having "premium" paywalls limit potential usages in their service from lower-class participants, to consequences as direct as having certain social network platforms inciting military coups and genocide in third-world countries as a result of ignoring their contributions to societal class divides [8].

This paper serves to compare the use of social networks from higher-class and lower-class individuals in a qualitative research study using a variety of metrics, to analyze if they produce similar or different volumes of data and usage analytics, to provide guidance as to when different focuses for social networks may be an appropriate approach to take.

3. METHODS

This study used the practice of data exports and downloads from social networks in order to obtain the necessary data points from participants, as well as collecting particular forms of data from authorized login sessions with each participant's social network accounts. Data obtained from authorized login sessions were logged and recorded manually and anonymously, whereas data obtained from data exports was extrapolated from their source files, before isolated and parsed in a Excel 365 spreadsheet via macros and selective importing.

To elaborate on the data gathered through the export process, we exported participants' data from Facebook Messenger through its "Download Your Information" tool [9], from Twitter Direct Messages through its "Download Data" service [10], from Snapchat through its "Download my Data" feature [11], and from Instagram Direct Messages through its "Download Data" feature [12]. From there, all exported data was converted from its source file type (usually JSON) into XML, before filtering the data only necessary for the study's three data parameters. Next, all filtered data was parsed and containerized through an XML-compatible macro, before being selectively imported into a master Excel 365 spreadsheet. For conflicting data, some imports from the macro needed manual review before being added to the spreadsheet in order to prevent overlaps, corrupted data points, or failed parsings. In a few instances, the macro parsed an entire dataset incorrectly, and required us to manually input it into the spreadsheet instead.

Three measures were used to analyze the relative effect that social class had on the behavior of users on social networks, these were: amount of active contacts, distance radius, and number of messages sent per day. All of these amounts are expressed in our data as averages, and have been used to give quantifiable data over these spreads of measures. Interview data was also gathered by exploring the views of study participants in relation to their digital data, its results & its conclusions. There is no established practice for analyzing the comparative depth and breadth of different qualitative methods within social network usages, to this end both the average number of active contacts and the average number of messages sent per day act as proxy measures of depth and breadth respectively. Excel 365 was used for calculations of totals and averages. Because of the small sample size no attempt to establish statistical significance was made.

Active Contacts

“Active Contacts” in this study are defined as contacts on a participant’s social network account that were spoken to within 90 days prior to the study’s start date. Frequency for chatting within those 90 days did not impact a contact’s label as an active contact.

Distance Radius

“Distance Radius” in this study is the average number of miles away that a participant’s list of active contacts are from them. Because this information relies on an Active Contacts’ privacy settings and the opt-in of public location information, not every Active Contact’s location was logged in the study. We also didn’t log the Distance Radius from private profiles of Active Contacts.

Number of Messages Per Day

“Number of Messages Per Day” in this study is the average amount of messages that a participant has with each of their Active Contacts.

4. RESULTS

Background

512 people submitted their data across all platforms and completed an interview. While the original pool of participants was 600, different individuals weren’t able to share their data among participating networks correctly - or weren’t able to complete our interview. Additionally, there were questions of how some questions may affect the character of an interview beyond the words directly attributable to that question. Average age of the two groups and average number of social network accounts were both comparable. Every participant was given \$1 for sharing their data and participating in an interview.

Characteristics of study’s participants

	Male	Female	Avg. Age	Avg. No. Of Accounts
High Class (273 part.)	151	122	26	7
Low Class (239 part.)	114	125	23	5

Overview averages of the study's participants across platforms

	High Class	Low Class	Difference
Amount of Contact Per Last 90 Days (Mean)	25(.7)	11(.5)	14(.2)
Distance Radius (Mean)	77 miles	19 miles	±58
Number of Messages Sent Per Day (Average)	58	77	±19

Data

Facebook Messenger

Facebook Messenger had the highest statistics amongst the other networks, and the highest rate of usage amongst participants compared to the other social networks - with over 90% of participants contributing to its averages. The difference in distance radius between social classes was at its highest with Messenger, while the difference between Active Contacts and Number of Messages were closest to the overview average. Distance radius for the Active Contacts of participants were calculated by taking the central coordinates of the town/city that each Active Contact labelled themselves as being from in their "About" section on their profile, and measuring its distance in relation from the participant's location.

FACEBOOK MESSENGER	High Class	Low Class	Difference
Amount of Active Contacts	28	10	±18
Distance Radius	97 miles	26 miles	±71
Number of Messages Per Day	47	70	±23

Instagram Direct Messages

Instagram Direct Messages had the second highest rate of usage amongst participants compared to the other social networks - with over 80% of participants contributing to its

averages. The difference in Amount of Active Contacts for Instagram Direct Messages was tied with Twitter Direct Messages. Distance radius for the Active Contacts of participants were calculated by taking the central coordinates of the town/city that each Active Contact labelled themselves as being from in their profile bio or photo locations, and measuring its distance in relation from the participant's location. Because of the lack of an official field to designate your location, Instagram was the hardest platform to evaluate the location for Active Contacts.

INSTAGRAM DIRECT MESSAGES	High Class	Low Class	Difference
Amount of Active Contacts	24	13	±11
Distance Radius	82 miles	15 miles	±67
Number of Messages Per Day	68	83	±15

Snapchat

Snapchat had a more youth-centered population - with over 70% of participants contributing to its averages. Distance radius for the Active Contacts of participants were calculated by Snapchat's built-in feature for telling a user how many miles their friends are away from the (if opted in), making it the easiest platform in our study for Distance Radius calculations.

SNAPCHAT	High Class	Low Class	Difference
Amount of Active Contacts	27	15	±12
Distance Radius	52 miles	11 miles	±41
Number of Messages Per Day	63	89	±26

Twitter Direct Messages

Twitter Direct Messages had the lowest statistics amongst the other networks, and the lowest rate of usage amongst participants compared to the other social networks - with under 70% of participants contributing to its averages.

TWITTER DIRECT MESSAGES	High Class	Low Class	Difference
Amount of Active Contacts	19	8	±11
Distance Radius	78 miles	25 miles	±53
Number of Messages Per Day	52	65	±13

5. DISCUSSION

This comparison of usage of social networks within lower-class and upper-class participants identified that both groups produced different averages for volumes of data (Active Contacts, Distance Radius, Number of Message) and a different breadth of topics (as explained below).

From Higher-Class Participants

Higher-class participants most frequently described their purpose on social networks as being used to acquire new forms of knowledge and to meet new people - mostly under the motivation of social entertainment. This is reflected in our dataset, since most higher-class participants utilized social networks for less frequent chats, and with little locational correlation between contacts. In most interviews, higher-class participants justified their higher-volume chats with others based only on the person's character or personality.

There was a spoken reverence for keeping a cultivated social circle from higher-class participants, in fact many had considered it a major contribution to their success, and an important attribute in their life to maintain. However, in interviews it was made clear that these social circle cultivations are not out of necessity for higher-class participants; but rather out of a desire for access, influence, and income that was at a social level above theirs. When asked why participants didn't put equal effort in creating social circles with individuals in social levels below theirs, they explained how those demographics can be a potential liability.

From Lower-Class Participants

Lower-class participants most frequently described their purpose on social networks as being used to maintain their existing communal relationships - and acquiring new relationships from within their community or social circles. This is also reflected in our dataset, since most lower-class participants utilized social networks to maintain

high-frequency chats with existing friends - with an overwhelming majority being local or within a restricted circle. Essentially, they used social networks to chat incessantly with immediate friends and family, and to stay up-to-date with them.

When asked the motives for these behaviors, lower-class participants most often described their approach on social networks as creating a sample size of community members to form rapports with in order to build and maintain stability in social connections and friendships - and using it as a reliable resource, which is generally sought out when in the absence of financial stability. This type of behavior is most often referred to as a method of “collectivist culture”.

Collectivism is an extremely common phenomenon in lower-income communities, as they give members within the community an assured reciprocity for helping those in need within their communities, while assuming that the same would be done for them when in need. This is a big reason why communities almost entirely on food stamps will put forth thousands when someone needs a hefty medical procedure- because they're relying on the same safety net.

When asking participants about the ramifications and consequences of collectivism, we were most often reminded of the lack of ability for its participants to leave depressed areas for more idealistic communities with more prosperous jobs; because their capital is tied up geographically. Leaving an area they collectively invested in would terminate their social connections, their social safety nets, their friendships and their social capital.

Our Reflection

In terms of rationalizing the outcome of our participants, the longer a person's experience of living within a social class, the more likely they are to see the potential in using certain tools to advance their goals, which they either have the necessity or privilege to attain and/or maintain based on their circumstances. These topics and their contextual parameters for different social classes had comprised a substantial proportion of the interviews with participants.

In terms of data collection, our methods were at the mercy of the competency of each of the four different social network's approaches at downloading and exporting a user's data. If there was a more empirical standard for social network data exports, we would have been able to autonomously gather participant's data in a comprehensive data cluster without nearly as many steps as we had to take along the way. Parsing,

extrapolating, data listings, and measurements of data were all hindrances that needed additional steps for our study's data strategy (as defined and described in the Results section).

6. CONCLUSION

These findings suggest that while higher-class individuals focus their efforts on using social networks to discover new content and individuals, lower-class individuals focus their efforts to maintain and strengthen their existing circles and connections - and to stay up to date with their life events via posts. In discussions, higher-class participants perceived their choices made on social networks as being made from their desires for entertainment, meeting new people, and learning new things. Lower-class participants, however, perceived their choices made on social networks as being made from necessity for a robust set of contacts based on their life circumstances.

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